

INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACH FOR ESTHETIC RESTORATION OF MISSING ANTERIOR TEETH WITH LIMITED INTER-ARCH SPACE

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ABSTRACT:

The essence of morpho-functional rehabilitation holds paramount importance in all aspects of prosthodontic procedures. When individuals pursue cosmetic dentistry, their foremost concern revolves around the aesthetics of their new smile. Fulfilling a patient's aspiration for an enhanced smile necessitates a comprehensive assessment to ensure both aesthetic appeal and long-term functionality. Successful prosthodontic treatments demand meticulous clinical and paraclinical evaluations, targeted interventions spanning bone, gums, teeth, and periodontium, and effective collaboration among the dentist, patient, and dental technician. This case report illustrates the utilization of inter-disciplinary approach to attain the desired esthetic outcomes for the patient.

Keywords: All ceramic, Esthetic, Golden proportion, Interarch, Inter-disciplinary.

INTRODUCTION:

Patients with missing anterior teeth typically present with issues such as a deviated midline, abnormal overlap, overbite, local bony discrepancies, and other functional problems. Overcoming these issues often requires a multidisciplinary approach.¹ Various treatment options can be considered for aesthetically and functionally replacing congenitally or traumatically missing anterior teeth. Some patients may be unwilling to undergo invasive implant surgery, leading them to choose less invasive fixed dental prostheses, which offer a stable and natural-looking alternative, good aesthetics, functional improvement, and preservation of the arch form.²

The type of prosthesis chosen also significantly influences achieving the patient's desired aesthetic outcome.¹ In cases where aesthetics are paramount, dental ceramics are the material of choice because they can effectively mimic the characteristics of natural tooth substance. All-ceramic fixed restorations provide the best aesthetic results due to the absence of metal components.³ The mechanical properties of these restorations are improved, and their susceptibility to fracture is reduced through the use of the resin-bonded technique.⁴

This case report outlines the restoration of anterior teeth through the utilization of a fixed dental prosthesis, coupled with surgical correction of the alveolar ridge. Immediate provisionalization was performed to establish correct gingival architecture and attain a natural emergence profile.

CASE REPORT:

A 40-year-old male patient reported to Department of Prosthodontics, Crown and Bridge of Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur with a chief complaint of missing teeth in upper front region of jaw for 1 month. Patient reported extraction of upper left lateral incisor one month back. Patient reported no medical history. Patient had habit of betel nut chewing for 10 years and stopped the habit in the last two and half years.

The clinical examination revealed missing 11,12,21,22,46. Remaining all teeth were present. Canine guided occlusion was present. Patient was having reduced mouth opening of 15cm as he was suffering from Stage III Oral Submucous Fibrosis and was advised medication and mouth exercises for the same. (Fig 1 –Fig 3)

FIG 1: FRONTAL VIEW

FIG 2: RIGHT SIDE VIEW

FIG 3: LEFT SIDE VIEW

Orthopantomograph revealed root piece with respect to 12. 23 showed reduced bone support mesially (Fig 4). Hence to suffice Ante's law and distribute the forces on canines, 1st premolar was also used as secondary abutment.

FIG 4: OPG

Mesio-distal and bucco-palatal bone width was measured on Cone Beam Computed Tomography in order to check bone architecture.

BUCCO-PALATAL WIDTH OF BONE IN ANTERIOR REGION
 Betⁿ 12 & 13- 9.62mm
 Betⁿ 11 & 12- 7.53mm
 Betⁿ 21 & 22- 9.03mm

MESIO-DISTAL DIMENSION PRESENT AT CRESTAL LEVEL
 26.45mm

Diagnostic casts were obtained and mounting was done on Hanau semi-adjustable articulator (Fig 5 –Fig 7)

FIG 5: FRONTAL VIEW

FIG 6: RIGHT LATERAL VIEW

FIG 7: LEFT LATERAL VIEW

Zenith matching with existing canine was done for central incisors and depending on that, zenith of lateral incisor i.e. 1mm below, was decided. Golden proportion rule was followed to determine the width of anteriors (Fig 8 –Fig 9).

FIG 8: INTER-CANINE DISTANCE FROM VISIBLE PART OF CANINE-

**FIG 9: CALCULATED WIDTHS –
CENTRAL INCISOR- 0.85CM
LATERAL INCISOR- 0.51CM**

Depending on inter-occlusal space available, 1-1.5mm of bone reduction on labial surface along with proclination of anterior teeth was necessary to accommodate and create adequate clearance between upper and lower anteriors (Fig 10). Bone reduction and wax mock-up was done on the cast (Fig 11).

FIG 10:1-1.5MM OF BONE REDUCTION ON DIAGNOSTIC

FIG 11: WAX MOCK-UP FOR TEMPORARY CROWNS

Patient underwent root canal treatment for 13 and 23 followed by tooth preparation of 13,14,23,24. Heatcure temporary prosthesis was made. Bone reduction surgery using peizoelectric surgery(Fig 12 – Fig 15).

FIG 12: FULL THICKNESS BUCCAL AND PALATAL FLAP

FIG 13: EXTRACTED ROOT PIECE WITH RESPECT TO 12

FIG 14: BONE REDUCTION EVALUATION USING TEMPORARY

FIG 15: TEMPORIZATION (AFTER 7 DAYS OF SURGERY)

Final all ceramic zirconia prosthesis was given

FIG 16: PRE-OPERATIVE

FIG 17: POST-OPERATIVE

DISCUSSION:

The effective rehabilitation of compromised cases hinges on a comprehensive approach that considers various factors, including:

Evaluating the space created by missing teeth to determine the most suitable prosthetic solution, such as partial dentures, bridges, or implant-supported restorations.

Assessing the alignment and condition of remaining teeth is crucial for treatment planning, taking into account factors like their health, position, stability, and potential need for extractions or orthodontic procedures.

Evaluation of available space, considering factors like overjet, overbite, crowding, or rotations, by assessing both the edentulous span and interarch relationship.

Classifying occlusion type (e.g., Class I, II, III) and considering its impact on functional harmony and stability.

Skeletal evaluation to gauge treatment feasibility, especially in cases with significant discrepancies in the maxilla-mandible relationship.

Piezosurgery, a relatively novel technique invented by Professor Vercelloti in 1988, offers advantages and overcomes the limitations of traditional instrumentation in oral bone surgery by modifying and improving conventional ultrasound technology⁵

Addressing midline discrepancies and deviations from the ideal centerline may require orthodontic or prosthodontic treatments, or a combination of both, to ensure both aesthetics and function. Thorough assessment of these factors enables dental professionals to develop customized treatment plans tailored to each patient's specific needs and circumstances, with the ultimate goal of achieving optimal functional and aesthetic outcomes.

CONCLUSION:

Rehabilitating the loss of anterior teeth poses a significant challenge in prosthodontics. The solution for such a clinical scenario depends on factors such as malocclusion, anterior relationship, specific space requirements, and the condition of adjacent teeth. Accurate diagnosis and thorough treatment planning with a multidisciplinary approach can address both the aesthetic and functional needs of patients, leading to long-term benefits for both the patient and dentist. This case report gives systematic approach to treat patient with limited interarch space and achieve satisfactory esthetic using interdisciplinary approach.

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